

Who is Professor Güell?

A short introduction about our Project coordinator and the story behind his vision.

Dr. Francisco Güell

Coordinator of the Mind-Brain Group of the Institute for Culture and Society, University of Navarra.

Dr. **Francisco Güell** is a researcher in the Institute of Culture and Society, part of the University of Navarra.

He holds two degrees, both in Biological Sciences and Philosophy, and teaches Bioethics Research at the Rey Juan Carlos University (Madrid). Author of the book "The biological and ontological status of the human embryo: the epigenetic paradigm of the 21st century from the theory of the essence of Xavier Zubiri", specialized in the epistemology of biology and the philosophical approach of Xavier Zubiri.

His research area is framed within the Philosophy of Biology and Neuroscience; he deals with problems related to the genetic and epigenetic dimension of organic development and the characterization of the unity of the living being, with research stays at King's College of London and Georgetown University.

"What inspired B2-InF is a beautiful story of self-reflection" – says Dr. Francisco Güell, Coordinator of the project.

It all began over ten years ago when a family friend asked him for recommendations regarding assisted reproduction technologies, trusting on his vast expertise in the realm of embryo development. But unfortunately, the question took him off-guard.

Dr. Güell realized that he did not know what to tell her, and this quickly became a frustration for him. He could not believe that he could not help a friend out with practical guidelines despite years of a professional career in the field.

It was at this moment that he decided to do anything in his power to change this. He then began his journey of research and analysis, which led him to explore some sides of ART processes from the axis of "responsibility", considering embryo development, patient, clinicians, publicity, and govern perspectives.

During this life journey, Dr. Güell quickly realized that Infertility awareness was lacking among the public. It was absurd that most people did not know that around 10% are now born in Spain thanks to infertility treatments. **Things had to change.**